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PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR DOCUMENT FORGERY IN THE ERA OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of crimes related to document forgery in the context of digital transformation and examines issues concerning the improvement of criminal liability for such offenses. The author substantiates that the development of electronic documents, electronic digital signatures, blockchain-based registries, and artificial intelligence technologies requires a renewed approach to the objective and subjective elements of a crime. The expansion of the concept of a document in the digital environment, along with deepfake technologies, electronic registry manipulation, and algorithmic mediation, complicates the establishment of causation in criminal qualification. At the same time, it is theoretically justified that artificial intelligence should not be regarded as a subject of crime but rather as an instrument for committing an offense. The article also analyzes issues of protecting digital documents within the framework of Article 228 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and proposes measures for legislative improvement, development of digital forensic institutions, and harmonization with international standards.

Keywords: digital transformation, document forgery, electronic document, artificial intelligence, corpus delicti, causation, deepfake technology, electronic digital signature, digital evidence, algorithmic mediation, transnational crime, improvement of criminal liability.

The process of digital transformation is recognized as one of the most important factors of legal development of the 21st century. Modern public administration, the financial system, education and healthcare are increasingly relying on digital infrastructure. Electronic document circulation, electronic digital signature, biometric identification, cloud technologies, blockchain-based registries and artificial intelligence algorithms serve to accelerate legal transactions, ensure transparency and reduce errors related to the human factor. At the same time, this process also creates new threats to legal security. In particular, digital forms of document forgery crimes are becoming more complex and multi-stage. In legal theory, the concept of a document has historically been interpreted as a material carrier that confirms official information. According to the classical criminal law approach, document forgery is the violation of legal transactions by changing the content of an official document or creating a

completely false document. However, in the context of digital transformation, the document itself has transformed from a material form into a record in an information system. A digital document is now not only a PDF or an electronic file, but also an entry in a state register, a transaction confirmed by an electronic signature, or a cryptographic record in a blockchain. In this regard, document forgery is also moving from traditional physical manipulation to algorithmic manipulation.

The criminal-legal consequences of digital transformation are widely discussed in the scientific literature. Some researchers consider the digital environment as a “new criminal arena” and emphasize the need to adapt offenses in it to the structure of traditional crimes [1]. Another group of scholars argues that digital crimes have their own characteristics and should be regulated on the basis of a separate criminal-legal concept [2]. The main difference between these approaches is how to interpret the transformed nature of the subject of the crime and the means of the crime.

Supporters of the concept of digital law see document forgery as an attack on information security. In their opinion, a digital document is a legally protected form of information resource, the violation or modification of which harms the trust infrastructure of society [3]. Within the framework of the theory of “trust infrastructure”, the authenticity of a document is interpreted as the basis for the stability of legal relations between the state and society [4]. If trust in an electronic registry or digital certificate weakens, the entire economic and administrative system may collapse.

Criminological studies also note a high level of latency of digital crimes. Digital manipulations often leave no physical traces, and the algorithmic “black box” complicates the determination of causality [5]. Therefore, some authors put forward the concept of “algorithmic responsibility” and propose the development of new criteria for determining guilt in crimes involving artificial intelligence and automated systems [6]. In this case, artificial intelligence is seen not as an independent subject, but as a source of danger.

The phenomenon of document forgery using artificial intelligence requires special attention. Deepfake technologies allow the artificial creation of a person’s signature, voice, or image. This is fundamentally different from traditional forgery. Now an algorithm is involved as a means of committing a crime. At the same time, the ability of the algorithm to make autonomous decisions creates theoretical problems in determining the nature of a crime. For example, if an artificial intelligence system automatically processes data and creates a false

certificate, who is responsible for this? The programmer who developed the system, the operator who used it, or an organization that did not control the system? Within the framework of the theory of legal determinism, it is emphasized that responsibility should always depend on the human factor. A person, as a conscious and volitional being, can be a subject of a crime, while artificial intelligence does not have such qualities. Therefore, the assessment of artificial intelligence as a means of crime is a priority approach in modern criminal law policy. However, this approach does not answer all questions, since the autonomy of digital systems can reduce human control [7].

Comparative legal studies show that many countries regulate digital document forgery as part of cybercrime. In European jurisprudence, high-risk artificial intelligence systems are subject to special control. In the United States, forgery of electronic documents is considered a federal crime. These experiences serve as an important source for improving national legislation.

This article is aimed at a comprehensive analysis of these theoretical and practical problems. In the context of digital transformation, new forms of document forgery crimes, their criminal-legal description and prospects for improving liability mechanisms are studied. The study uses a normative-legal analysis, a comparative approach and a conceptual model. The goal is to develop scientifically based proposals that ensure a balance between innovation and legal security.

Thus, in the era of digital transformation, document forgery crimes are not only a technological problem, but also a fundamental criminal-legal problem. A deep scientific analysis of this issue and adaptation of the institution of liability to modern threats should become a priority task of criminal policy.

In the context of digital transformation, the concept of “document” has gone beyond the traditional paper-based official act and has begun to encompass electronic data carriers, database records, files certified by an electronic digital signature, biometric identification data, QR codes, and blockchain-based registry entries. This process has created the need to interpret the legal essence of a document based on a functional approach. As L. Lessig noted, in the digital environment, “code” becomes a means of normative regulation, and legal relations are formed through software architecture [8]. This approach indicates the need to evaluate a document not only in terms of its material form, but also in terms of its functional and informational content.

Russian lawyers have also paid attention to the issue of the legal status of digital documents. V.N. Lopatin notes that in the process of using digital

technologies, the identification, authentication, and verification functions of a document should be considered as the main criteria [9]. This idea serves as an important theoretical basis for identifying new forms of document forgery. Because in the digital environment, forgery is often carried out not by violating the external form of a document, but by violating its identification mechanisms.

Deepfake technologies based on artificial intelligence allow for high-fidelity simulation of a person's image, voice, or signature. R. Chesney and D. Citron assess the phenomenon of deepfake as a serious threat to privacy, democratic processes, and national security [10]. These technologies also have a negative impact on official document authentication systems. For example, electronic documents based on biometric identification can be fraudulently created or verified through deepfake.

Russian scientist M.N. Marchenko notes that actions committed using artificial intelligence complicate classical criminal law constructs [11]. Deepfake technologies require a new approach to determining the objective side of a crime, since document forgery is often carried out through algorithmic manipulation.

In the context of digital public administration, registers (cadastre, population census, tax databases) are the main source of legal information. F. Pasquale criticizes the lack of transparency of algorithmic systems and limited control over data in the concept of a "black box society" [12]. Changing official records through illegal access to electronic registers is emerging as a new form of document falsification.

Russian criminal law doctrine emphasizes that illegal interference with a database can be equated with tampering with the content of a document [13]. In this case, the physical form of the document is preserved, but its information content is manipulated. Therefore, the objective side of the crime is expressed in the illegal impact on the digital system.

Electronic digital signature (EDS) is the main means of confirming the authenticity of a document in modern legal practice. However, issuing a document on behalf of another person by using EDS or stealing keys has become a common form of falsification. Such actions violate not the appearance of the document, but its authentication mechanism.

G. Hallevy justifies the need to attribute responsibility for actions committed using artificial intelligence to the human factor [14]. In cases of illegal use of an electronic signature, responsibility is not borne by the algorithm, but by the person who used it.

Blockchain technology is interpreted as an immutable registry. However, the reliability of documents can be violated by hiding transactions, entering incorrect information, or manipulating the consensus mechanism. R. Brownsword emphasizes that legal transactions are undermined when the normative architecture of the digital infrastructure is violated [15].

B.Kh. Ruziev notes that the boundary between the subject and the means of a crime in the conditions of digitalization has become more complicated [16]. In cases of blockchain manipulation, the objective side of the crime is manifested by encroachment on data integrity.

To identify and qualify crimes of document forgery in the digital environment, it is necessary to combine the functional-legal approach, information security theory, and the concept of algorithmic responsibility. J. Burrell, analyzing the problem of algorithmic transparency, shows that the “black box” model makes it difficult to determine the causal connection [17].

Thus, the digital transformation has fundamentally changed the forms and methods of document forgery crimes. Now the crime can be committed not only by physically changing the document, but also by manipulating the digital system, breaking identification mechanisms, or using algorithmic means. This requires new methodological approaches and normative improvements in determining the objective side of the crime.

In the context of digital transformation, crimes related to document forgery require a revision of classical criminal law constructs. In the traditional interpretation, the objective side of the crime is considered to consist of a socially dangerous act (or inaction), a socially dangerous consequence, a causal connection, and a method of commission. The subjective side includes the form of guilt, intent or negligence, motive, and purpose. However, in the digital environment, the content of these elements is becoming more complex, as document forgery crimes are committed using algorithmic tools, automated systems, and artificial intelligence technologies.

In classical criminal law theory, the objective side is manifested through socially dangerous behavior that has an external expression. In the Russian legal school, the objective side is interpreted as a set of external signs of a crime [18]. However, in the digital environment, document forgery is often committed not by manipulating the material form of the document, but by manipulating the record in the database, an electronic signature, or an authentication mechanism. In this case, the external expression of the crime is carried out through invisible algorithmic processes.

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F. Pasquale, analyzing the phenomenon of the algorithmic “black box”, notes that the decision-making process in complex technological systems is not transparent [19]. This approach shows how difficult it is to establish a cause-and-effect relationship in determining the objective side of a crime. For example, if a legal consequence arose as a result of changing data through illegal access to an electronic register, then the external act of the crime may not have been committed by a person, but by means of a software code.

R. Brownsword, emphasizing the role of digital infrastructure as a “normative architecture”, notes that actions carried out through code should also be subject to the criteria of legal liability [20]. Thus, the objective side is now expressed not only by physical change, but also by illegal interference with the digital system.

B.Kh. Ruziev also emphasizes the need to take into account the criteria of information security when determining the objective side of a crime in the context of digitization. Since falsification of documents is often associated with a violation of data integrity.

It should be noted that in the traditional criminal law interpretation, the means and method are considered as aggravating circumstances of a crime. However, the importance of methods and tools in the digital environment is such that artificial intelligence, deepfakes, and automated scripts are shaping new ways of committing crimes. R. Chesney and D. Citron show that deepfakes allow for the falsification of the authenticity of a document by compromising personal identity [21].

G. Hallevy justifies the need to determine the responsibility for actions committed by means of artificial intelligence depending on the human factor. This approach is important in reinterpreting the objective side, since the action is performed not directly by a person, but by an algorithm.

The subjective side of the composition of the crime in the classical interpretation is determined by the form of guilt. According to V.V. Luneev, guilt is the main element expressing the psychological attitude of the crime [22]. In the digital environment, determining intent becomes more complicated. For example, if an artificial intelligence system produces an incorrect result, the question arises whether the user’s intent was directly aimed at falsification or not.

M.N. Marchenko notes that the probabilistic operation of artificial intelligence requires a revision of the classical categories of guilt. In this case, the concept of negligence also acquires a new meaning. If the system is known in

advance to cause a dangerous consequence, but the user has not exercised the necessary control, the subjective side can manifest itself in the form of negligence.

J. Burrell, analyzing the problem of algorithmic transparency, shows that it is difficult to assess the consequence without controlling the human decision-making process. This complicates the definition of intent and negligence.

Crime in the digital environment often occurs as a result of the interaction between a person and an algorithm. L. Lessig shows the normative effect of code in the concept of “code is law”. If the code is forming a legal consequence, the role of a person in setting program parameters should be taken into account when determining the subjective side.

N.V. Korbut emphasizes that the level of conscious human intervention and control should be the main criteria for determining responsibility in digital crimes. This approach is an important theoretical basis for reinterpreting the subjective side.

The above scientific views show that digital transformation requires a reinterpretation of the objective and subjective aspects of the structure of the crime. The objective side is now expressed not only in material action, but also in illegal interference with the digital system. The subjective side should be determined in connection with the role of a person in the algorithmic process, the level of control and the ability to foresee the risk.

Therefore, while maintaining the classical criminal law constructions in qualifying the crimes of document forgery, it is necessary to reinterpret them in accordance with the characteristics of the digital environment. This forms the theoretical and practical basis for improving criminal law in accordance with the requirements of the digital era.

In addition, based on the above, the need to improve national legislation is manifested in the following.

That is, in our opinion, the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for liability for document forgery. However, in the context of digital transformation, it is necessary to clarify the following issues:

clear definition of electronic documents and digital records as the subject of a crime;

recognition of the use of artificial intelligence as a qualifying sign;

introduction of a separate mechanism for cross-border crimes;

procedural strengthening of digital evidence.

It is also important to prioritize the human factor in determining the subject of liability. Artificial intelligence remains a tool, and liability rests with the person who controls or uses it.

The EU's regulatory approach to Artificial Intelligence imposes special requirements on high-risk systems. In the US and European countries, crimes related to the forgery of digital documents are also qualified as cybercrime.

Strengthening international cooperation mechanisms is important, since many forgery operations are carried out through servers in other jurisdictions.

In the context of digital transformation, crimes related to document forgery pose complex challenges not only for the technological, but also for the regulatory and legal system. Therefore, the issue of improving the institution of criminal liability in line with modern digital threats requires a systematic, comprehensive and forward-looking approach. This process should simultaneously provide for ensuring regulatory clarity, developing the infrastructure of technological expertise, updating qualification marks, strengthening preventive mechanisms, and ensuring international harmonization. First of all, it is necessary to interpret the concept of "document" broadly. In the traditional criminal law construction, a document is often considered a written act with a material carrier. In the digital environment, a document can exist in the form of an electronic file, a record in a database, a blockchain registry, biometric identification data, or an electronic certificate. Therefore, in the regulatory provisions defining the elements of a crime, it is necessary to clearly define such categories as "electronic document", "digital data carrier", and "automated registry entry".

Normative clarity is necessary not only for the correct qualification of a crime, but also for determining the causal link and assessing the form of guilt. Separately defining the legal force of digital documents, authentication criteria and identification mechanisms in a criminal law context ensures uniformity in law enforcement practice.

Also, the inclusion of terms such as "digital manipulation" and "algorithmic interference" in the provisions simplifies the determination of the objective aspect of the crime. This serves to establish clear boundaries of the composition of the crime.

The second important direction is the development of a special digital forensics institute. In the process of identifying and proving crimes of forgery of digital documents, it is necessary to analyze algorithmic processes, code structure, log files and cryptographic traces. Therefore, traditional forensic methods are not enough.

Special digital forensics centers should be able to detect deepfake materials created using artificial intelligence, analyze blockchain transactions and verify electronic signature authentication. In this regard, it is important to establish cooperation between state bodies, research centers and private technology companies.

Digital forensics serves not only to collect evidence, but also to determine the cause-and-effect relationship, open the algorithmic “black box” and identify direct or indirect human intervention. This creates the necessary methodological basis for the correct interpretation of the objective and subjective aspects of the crime.

The third promising direction is to define the use of artificial intelligence as an aggravating circumstance. If the crime of document forgery is committed using artificial intelligence technologies, its social danger increases. Because such tools have the ability to harm a large number of individuals on a large scale, with high accuracy.

Therefore, it is advisable to include the circumstance “committed using artificial intelligence” as a separate qualifying characteristic in the structure of the crime. This will allow for a more precise determination of the severity of the crime and individualization of the punishment.

However, when introducing such a sign, the concept of interpreting artificial intelligence as a means of committing a crime, rather than a subject of a crime, should be preserved. Responsibility will still depend on the human factor.

The fourth direction is to strengthen preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing crime. The use of multi-stage authentication, cryptographic protection, and blockchain-based records in state registers and electronic document circulation systems ensures the integrity of documents.

Also, monitoring systems based on artificial intelligence allow for the automatic detection of suspicious transactions. For example, the system can automatically send a warning when unusual changes are observed in the database.

The effectiveness of preventive measures is also associated with raising legal awareness and training. Employees of judicial, investigative, and expert bodies should regularly improve their skills in digital technologies.

Crimes of digital document forgery are often of a cross-border nature. Servers may be located in one country, users in another, and victims in a third country. Therefore, strengthening international cooperation is urgent.

It is necessary to adapt to international standards, develop cooperation within the framework of conventions against cybercrime, and improve

information exchange mechanisms. The creation of rapid information exchange systems between judicial authorities will increase the effectiveness of detecting crimes.

The above areas should be implemented as a complementary system. Regulatory clarity will yield effective results only when combined with technological expertise, and qualifying signs with preventive mechanisms.

Digital transformation is shifting the criminal legal system to a dynamic, rather than static, path of development. Therefore, improving criminal liability should not be limited to increasing punishment, but should be implemented on the basis of a comprehensive model that includes regulatory clarity, technological security, and international cooperation.

In conclusion, document forgery crimes are taking on new forms and forms in the digital era. To effectively counter these threats, it is an urgent task to harmonize the institution of criminal liability with modern technological realities, clarify the regulatory framework, develop digital forensics, establish the use of artificial intelligence as a qualification, and ensure harmonization with international standards. Reforms in these areas will serve to ensure legal stability in digital circulation and strengthen public security.

In the era of digital transformation, document forgery crimes have reached a qualitatively new level. Artificial intelligence and other digital technologies are now widely used as a means of committing crimes. This requires a revision of criminal law institutions in accordance with modern threats.

Artificial intelligence is not an independent criminal subject, but it can become an aggravating factor in criminal liability as a means of committing crimes. It is possible to effectively combat document forgery crimes in the digital environment by improving legislation, strengthening digital evidence, and strengthening international cooperation.

Thus, ensuring a balance between innovation and legal security should become a priority of criminal policy.

The analysis of the article shows that in the context of digital transformation, document forgery crimes are becoming new threats that are completely different from traditional forms, having a high-tech nature. Cases of forgery committed using electronic documents, biometric data, blockchain registries and artificial intelligence tools require new methodological approaches to criminal-legal assessment.

In this regard, it is appropriate to put forward the following proposals and conclusions:

strengthen the concept of “digital document” as a separate legal category in criminal law;

establish document forgery using artificial intelligence as a qualifying aggravating circumstance;

institutionally develop institutions of digital forensics and algorithmic examination;

strengthen mechanisms of international cooperation against cross-border digital crimes;

improve cryptographic protection of state registers and electronic identification systems.

Thus, the task of criminal law in the digital era is to ensure a balance between innovation and security, and to effectively regulate the risks associated with the use of technologies, while keeping the human being at the center as the subject of crime..

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